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Determinants of the development of the national innovation system

The subject of the study. *In modern conditions of economic growth in the period of globalization, innovation is an important prerequisite for development. Their role and importance is constantly growing, turning into a dominant source of economic development, growth in the volume of export–import operations, increasing the level of competitiveness of enterprises, and the standard of living of the population. An important place in the development of innovations is occupied by the national innovation system, which consists of clusters, industrial parks, technological and scientific parks, technopolises, etc.*

The purpose of the study. *The purpose of the article is to study the theoretical and methodological aspects of the national innovation system and the current state of development of one of its components – clusters.*

Research methods. *The main research methods used include description, analysis, generalization, etc.*

Work results. *The article examined the main approaches to the theory of the innovation system. In the theoretical and methodological aspect, the existing interpretations of the concept of «national innovation system» based on the application of various approaches are analyzed. Among them, the interpretation of the concept of «national innovation system» by such scientists as V. Bilozubenko, Z. Mykytyuk, M. Pashuta, L. Fedulova, L. Yaremko, etc. was noted.*

Conclusions. *The authors of the article investigated the peculiarities of the creation and development of the main components of the national innovation system, which are located on the territory of the Ivano–Frankivsk region. In particular, this applies to clusters and industrial parks. The existing*

regulatory and legal support in the direction of the functioning of clusters and industrial parks was also analyzed. Proposals were developed regarding their further functioning in the Ivano–Frankivsk region.

The practical significance of the obtained results in terms of the development of proposals for the creation and development of elements of the national innovation system is beyond doubt.

Keywords: cluster, cluster initiatives, industrial park, economic development, globalization.

БОЙКО О. М.
КУЧЕРЕНКО С. Ю.

Детермінанти розвитку національної інноваційної системи

Предмет дослідження. В сучасних умовах економічного зростання в період глобалізації важливою передумовою розвитку є інновації. Їх роль та значення постійно зростає, перетворюючись на домінуюче джерело економічного розвитку, зростання обсягу експортно–імпорتنих операцій, підвищення рівня конкурентоспроможності підприємств, рівня життя населення. Вагоме місце в розвитку інновацій посідає національна інноваційна система, яка складається з кластерів, індустріальних парків, технологічних та наукових парків, технополісів тощо.

Мета дослідження полягає у дослідженні теоретико–методологічних аспектів національної інноваційної системи та сучасного стану розвитку однієї з її складових – кластерів.

Методи дослідження. До основних методів дослідження, які були використані слід віднести опис, аналіз, узагальнення тощо.

Результати роботи. В статті було досліджено основні підходи щодо теорії інноваційної системи. В теоретико–методологічному аспекті проаналізовано існуючі трактування поняття «національна інноваційна система» в основу яких покладено застосування різноманітних підходів. Серед них було відмічено трактування поняття «національної інноваційної системи» такими вченими як Білозубенко В., Микитюк З., Пашута М., Федулова Л., Яремко Л. та ін.

Висновки. Авторами статті було досліджено особливості створення та розвитку основних складових національної інноваційної системи, які розташовані на території Івано–Франківської області. Зокрема це стосується кластерів та індустріальних парків. Також було проаналізовано існуюче нормативно–правове забезпечення у напрямку функціонування кластерів, індустріальних парків. Було розроблено пропозиції щодо їх подальшого функціонування в Івано–Франківській області.

Практична значимість одержаних результатів в частині розробки пропозицій щодо створення та розвитку елементів національної інноваційної системи не викликає сумнівів.

Ключові слова: кластер, кластерні ініціативи, індустріальний парк, економічний розвиток, глобалізація.

Introduction. B. Lundvall, R. Nelson, and K. Freeman are the founders of the issue of formation of the national innovation system. The works of Y. Bazhal, V. Heyts, I. Yehorov, John Stanley Metcalf, P. Patel, M. Porter, A. Rickne, B. Santo, L. Fedulova, etc.

Over the past few years, there has been a deepening of the issue of the development of the national system. Of scientific interest are the studies of V. Zakharchenko and V. Kandeeva (2018), who in the published work examined the theoretical provisions and determined the essence and content of the national innovation system. An analysis of the international experience of the development of the national innovation system of countries with developed economies was carried out. We considered the tools of influence of state policy on innovative activity.

O. Khymenko (2019) clarified the issues related to the principles and ways of improving the state policy regarding the activation of the development of the national innovation system in Ukraine.

In his works, I. Borysov (2020) conducted a study of the formation of the national innovation system and identified the shortcomings of its formation in Ukraine. Unlike I. Borisov, authors such as O. Boyko and S. Kucherenko (2020) in their work consider the components of the national innovation system using the example of the G7 countries in the period of globalization challenges.

The research of O. Khymenko and I. Yehorov (2020) focuses on issues of management decision in the innovative activity of the business entity. We also consider the issue of research into the national

innovation system, which is presented by university science specialists, to be a significant development. In particular, they were reflected in the writings of Y. Bazhal (2021), who considered the policy of smart specialization as a form of state innovation policy. Attention is paid to the issue of involving universities in the strategy of smart specialization in the context of creating basic innovations.

The research of S. Tyutyunnikova and O. Fridman (2020) consisted in the study of the current state of the national innovation system of entrepreneurship and the essence of public–private partnership in innovation.

Modern trends of the country's economic development in the conditions of globalization are reflected in the innovative development model. This led to the manifestation of radical changes that gave impetus to the formation and development of the national innovation system. This is an effective mechanism for the development of competitiveness, economic growth, improvement of quality and improvement of the population's standard of living.

The purpose of the article is to investigate the issue of the formation of the national innovation system, to determine its essence and its components, which are considered on the example of the Ivano–Frankivsk region.

The main tasks of the research should include: definition of the interpretation of the essence of «national innovation system»; the regularities of the development of the national innovation system are considered; the peculiarities of the development of clusters and industrial parks in the Ivano–Frankivsk region, as constituent elements of the national innovation system, were analyzed; researched the legal framework for the creation and development of elements of the national innovation system in the region; proposals were developed regarding the further functioning of clusters and industrial parks in the region.

Materials and methods. We consider it expedient to include the main stages of the research: defining the interpretation of the essence of the «national innovation system»; identifying patterns of development of the national innovation system; monitoring of the specifics of the development of clusters and industrial parks in the Ivano–Frankivsk region; research of regulatory and legal support regarding the creation and development of elements of the national innovation system in the region; development of a proposal for the further functioning of clusters and industrial parks in the region.

The main research methods used include description, analysis, generalization, etc.

Results and discussion/ Modern trends of the country's economic development in the conditions of globalization are reflected in the innovative development model. This led to the manifestation of radical changes that gave impetus to the formation and development of the national innovation system. This is an effective mechanism for the development of competitiveness, economic growth, improvement of quality and improvement of the population's standard of living.

The founders of the theory of the national innovation system are considered to be B.–A. Lundvala, R. Nelson, K. Freeman. The founders of this theory used different approaches to the interpretation of the essence of the concept of «national innovation system», which is due to different research tasks, views on economic phenomena and processes. In particular, K. Freeman (1995) defines the national innovation system as «a system of institutions in the public and private sectors, the activities and interactions between which are aimed at initiating, importing, modifying and diffusing new technologies». Unlike K. Freeman, B.–A. Lundval understands the concept of «national innovation system» as organizations and institutions involved in research and research, for example, research and development departments, technological institutes and universities (Varblane, Dyker & Tamm, 2007). It is worth noting that R. Nelson understood the «national innovation system» as a number of institutions, the interaction of which determines the innovative activity of domestic firms (Shapovalova, 2011).

It is worth noting that, in contrast to the classical interpretations of the concept of «national innovation system», various approaches are proposed, among which the following can be distinguished:

- The national innovation system is a set of institutions (organizations) that create favorable conditions for the implementation of innovation processes. Thus, the OECD reports state that the national innovation system is a set of institutions of the private and public sectors, which individually and in cooperation determine the development and spread of new technologies within a certain country.

A similar point of view is shared by V. Bilozubenko (2009), defining the national innovation system as a complex of interdependent institutions of organizational and legal nature, connected by a special structure, which ensure the flow of the nation–

al innovation process, its individual stages, as well as the participation and regulatory role of the state in the field of innovative development. At the same time, he notes that the national innovation system is the «core of the economy» based on knowledge, because it ensures the practical implementation of new knowledge in the form of innovations. In our opinion, this approach to the interpretation of the essence of the national innovation system emphasizes only the infrastructural and security component of the national innovation system.

– The national innovation system is a set of organizations that directly participate in the innovation process. In particular, L. Yaremko (2007) considers the national innovation system as a set of interconnected organizations (structures) engaged in the production and commercial implementation of scientific knowledge and technologies within national borders. It is worth noting that Z. Mykytyuk (2006) defines the national innovation system as «a set of interconnected institutions designed to create, preserve and transfer knowledge, skills and artifacts that define new technologies».

This approach focuses attention only on institutions that directly participate in the innovation process, leaving aside those that provide favorable conditions for the implementation of innovative activities.

– The national innovation system is a set of organizations that directly participate in the innovation process, as well as institutions that create favorable conditions for its implementation. For example, Fedulova L. and Pashuta M. (2005) note that «the national innovation system is a set of interconnected organizations (structures) engaged in the production and commercialization of scientific knowledge and technologies within national borders, small and large companies, universities, laboratories, technology parks and incubators, as a complex of institutions of a legal, financial and social nature, which ensure innovative processes and have strong national roots, traditions, political and cultural features».

Other experts, such as Kavtysh O. and Grechko A. (2011) consider the national innovation system as a dynamic, open, structured subsystem of the international innovation system. It consists of interconnected actively cooperating institutions and supporting institutions that are involved in the process of creation, accumulation and implementation of scientific knowledge, techniques and technologies, taking into account the legal, economic, organizational,

socio-cultural conditions of the innovation process within the national economy, based on the strategy of scientific and technological development. Its main goal should be to increase the competitiveness of the economy and the standard of living of the population.

S. Metcalf interprets the national innovation system as a set of certain institutions that jointly or individually contribute to the development and spread of new technologies, provide the basis for the formation and implementation of state policy, which directly affects the innovation process; it is a system of interconnected institutions that creates, preserves, and transmits the knowledge, skills, and artifacts that define new technologies.

In the order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of June 17, 2009 No. 680p «On the approval of the Concept of the development of the national innovation system» (expired in 2021), it was noted that the national innovation system is «a set of legislative, structural and functional components (institutions), which are involved in the process of creation and application of scientific knowledge and technologies, determine the legal, economic, organizational and social conditions of the innovation process within national borders and ensure the growth of the competitiveness of domestic organizations and enterprises due to the increase of their innovative activity» (Order, 2009).

In our opinion, the advantage of this approach is to focus on the unity of the base and superstructure of the national innovation system as an important prerequisite for the effective implementation of innovation processes.

Among the regularities of the development of the national innovation system, the following should be highlighted:

- the innovation system is an open system that is closely connected with other systems;
- the state plays an active role in the formation and functioning of the national innovation system;
- the development of innovative technologies, in particular innovative and telecommunication technologies, contributes to the creation of network structures based on the principles of self-organization (synergy);
- increasing the importance of the role of regions in the process of innovation development;
- as part of the process of globalization, as national innovation systems develop, their integration into supranational and other systems takes place.

It is worth noting that Bagrova I. and Cherevko O. (2010) note in their research that there are two

subsystems of the national innovation system: the subsystem of knowledge generation and dissemination and the subsystem of innovation infrastructure. Therefore, it is worth considering some components of the innovative infrastructure, among which clusters are gaining significant importance.

A significant number of clusters operate in the USA – 380 units, Italy – 206, Hungary – 176, Great Britain – 168, Poland – 161, India – 106, France – 96, the Czech Republic – 74, Romania – 51, Ukraine – more than 50 units, Denmark – 34, Germany – 32, Lithuania – 25, the Netherlands – 20, Latvia – 15, Slovakia – 11, Finland – 9 units (Assessment, 2023).

In Ukraine, clusters should be considered as a qualitatively new form of management and an important prerequisite for the introduction at the regional level of an innovative model of economic development, taking into account the specifics of the Ukrainian economic and management systems, ensuring appropriate regulatory and legal support. At the same time, taking into account the experience of building a cluster network in the leading countries of the world, which have achieved significant success in high rates of national/regional/local development, is of particular importance. So, in particular, the territory of Ivano–Frankivsk region stands out among other regions of Ukraine as a favorable environment for the development of small and medium–sized businesses; the availability of free land plots and production areas suitable for the creation of industrial, technological, innovative; close location to EU borders, investment attractiveness; developed education system, available scientific and personnel potential; the location of the region in the western part of the country in close proximity to the existing and promising international railway and road corridors: «Crete 5», «Europe–Asia», «North–South», etc. Therefore, within the borders of the Ivano–Frankivsk region, there is a cluster for the production of souvenirs «Constellation», which unites 19 masters of bed–making from the village of Yavorova and 16 – from the city of Kosova.

In the Ivano–Frankivsk region, there is also a cluster «Clothing and other artistic crafts in Prykarpattia», which specializes in the production of products from sheep's wool. In accordance with the order of the regional state administration dated 22.07.2002 No. 525 «On the development and implementation of the system of cluster models of regional development» and with the aim of supporting the develop-

ment of small business structures and the region, a project of the program (third stage) of the cluster model of the organization of production «Leaving and others» was developed folk art crafts in Prykarpattia» (Regulation of the regional state administration dated 06.05.2005 No. 176 On the project of the program (third stage) of the cluster model of the organization of production «Lizhnikarstvo and other folk art crafts in Prykarpattia»). The document provides for the creation of a cluster that would contribute to the revival, preservation, protection and development of folk handicrafts; the creation of favorable economic conditions and a legal field for the implementation of entrepreneurial activities by the masters of folk handicrafts; the organization of individual producers – masters of folk handicrafts with the aim of eliminating shadow production, the creation of official jobs, which, in turn, it will ensure the receipt of a certain stable income, social protection and social insurance for workers; ensuring the powers and rights of territorial communities for local self–government in the field of local budget revenue generation from business activities carried out in the relevant territory and their optimization for the purpose of socio–economic development of such communities.

The Carpathian National University, entrepreneurs, representatives of district and regional state administrations took an active part in the creation of cluster initiatives within Ivano–Frankivsk region. The form of development of folk crafts was chosen as a voluntary association of individual producers, entrepreneurs, research institutions, state and local authorities, financial and intermediary organizations within a certain territorially formed community for highly effective cooperation, which fully corresponds to the essence of the cluster.

In addition to the cluster of initiatives mentioned above, the Tysmenytskyi fur cluster (JSC «Khutro–firma Tysmenytsia», LLP JV «Tykaferlyuks») is successfully functioning within the limits of the Ivano–Frankivsk region. The high level of qualification of the personnel of the fur cluster contributes to the functioning of small enterprises engaged in harvesting and processing of leather, production of headgear and fur clothing and their trade.

It should be noted that it is expedient to create a cluster of producers of sewing products on the basis of joint–stock companies «Halychyna», «Kolomiyskaya Sewing Factory», which are actively working for foreign markets, and other 39 large

and medium-sized enterprises of the industry that produce ready-made clothes, underwear, textiles products, curtains. Small enterprises of the industry can also become participants in such a cluster, which would allow each of them not only to consistently improve the conditions for the development of new high-quality products that meet fashion trends and consumer needs, to increase exports, but also to use economic means to replace the distribution schemes inherent in «large» production.

It is also of interest to create a forest industry cluster, the participants of which can become the majority of enterprises of the region (timber mills, wood-working factories, furniture manufacturing factories). The woodworking industry, which is a priority in the region's economy, has been increasing the output of sawmill products, construction parts made of wood and wood-based boards, plywood, paper and cardboard, and furniture for the past three years.

«Interplit» joint venture has become a leader in the woodworking industry of Ukraine and supplies a wide range of high-quality laminated and chipboards to the domestic market and to 19 countries around the world. «Promin-Halychyna» produces school furniture of modern design, competitive in Ukraine and abroad. The reconstruction and technical re-equipment of production, the introduction of the latest wood processing technologies and the development of new types of products were observed at Uniplyt, Vyhoda woodworking plant, Interior, Ivano-Frankivsk woodworking plant, OIPas, West-Wood», enterprises of the corporation «Halychyna – Forest», at the Experimental Plant «Prut», «Ivano-Frankivsk Furniture Factory».

In wartime conditions on the territory of Ukraine, the issue of reforming hospital districts in the Ivano-Frankivsk region has gained relevance. According to the new approach, the network of health care facilities, united in one hospital district, is additionally divided into 5 medical clusters (Ivano-Frankivsk, Kalusky, Kolomyisky, Nadvirnyansky and Kosivsko-Verkhovynsky clusters). According to the types of medical care provided in the health care facilities of the hospital cluster, the network of facilities will be divided into cluster, supra-cluster and general hospitals. The cluster institution is multidisciplinary, able to provide the population's need for medical services on the territory of the hospital district. It will provide basic directions of medical care, stabilization of the patient's condition and routing to cluster and su-

per-cluster healthcare facilities. It will provide assistance to up to 40,000 people living within a radius of up to 60 km (The creation). The main areas of specialization are neurology, infectious diseases, therapy, surgery, etc. As we can see, the main goal of restructuring the industry should be the functioning of a capable network of health care facilities that will guarantee the provision of effective and affordable medical care to the population.

One of the important issues of the post-war revival of the economy of Ukraine, and in particular of the Ivano-Frankivsk region, is the creation of national food industry corporations for children's nutrition based on clusters.

Participants in the creation and functioning of the cluster are: enterprises that specialize in priority types of economic activity; firms supplying goods/services for specialized enterprises; enterprises (organizations, firms) engaged in maintenance of public industries (transport, energy, environmental protection infrastructure); market infrastructure organizations (consulting, audit, insurance, credit, etc.); non-commercial and public organizations, associations of entrepreneurs, chambers of commerce and industry; research, development and educational organizations; organizations of innovative infrastructure, small and medium-sized business support infrastructure (industrial parks, technology parks, business incubators, technology transfer centers, energy saving centers, subcontracting support centers); centers and agencies for the development of entrepreneurship, regional and municipal development, attraction of investments, agencies for the support of export of goods, state and municipal funds for the support of entrepreneurship, funds for the promotion of lending, etc.

The cluster can be created according to one of several existing scenarios: «from the bottom up» (separate projects and programs integrating potential participants of the cluster); «from top to bottom» (creation of advisory and monitoring bodies, cluster development strategies); mixed (combination of the features of two paths «from the bottom up» and «from the top down»).

The creation and development of clusters plays an important role in the formation of the economic environment of the region, since, depending on the type, they contribute to:

- intensification of innovative activities due to the accumulation of commercial and industrial knowl-

edge in clusters; creation of innovations due to internal competition between producers of the cluster; acceleration of the introduction of innovations as a result of cooperation between manufacturers and suppliers, etc.;

- development of high-tech industries;
- the growth of the gross domestic product, tax revenues to the budgets due to the attraction of investments, including foreign, funds from local budgets to finance innovative projects of technology and infrastructure development within the framework of public-private partnership projects, mutual lending of cluster participants, etc.;
- activation of the development of small and medium-sized businesses in old industrial regions; – growth of the share of exports of manufactured products;
- creation of unique opportunities for the training of highly qualified specialists outside the boundaries of industry training (exchange of experience, cluster training centers, etc.).

Summarizing what has been said, we note that clusters are a modern form of enterprise integration capable of increasing the competitive advantages of each cluster-participating firm; international experience shows a high level of efficiency of their functioning; in each country there are peculiarities of cluster development; the specificity of the cluster is obtaining a synergistic effect, which is manifested by the growth of competitiveness, and its distinguishing feature is innovative orientation; issues of financing the creation and development of clusters are concentrated on budgetary resources or investor resources.

The basis for innovative activity based on the creation and development of clusters in Ukraine is more than 200 normative legal acts. These are the Constitution of Ukraine, the Land Code of Ukraine, the Tax Code of Ukraine; Budget Code of Ukraine, Law of Ukraine «On Land Leasing», Law of Ukraine «On Priority Areas of Innovative Activity», Law of Ukraine «On Regulation of Town Planning Activities», Law of Ukraine «On Scientific and Scientific and Technical Activities», Law of Ukraine «On Higher Education», the Law of Ukraine «On the Principles of National Security», the Law of Ukraine «On Cross-Border Cooperation», the Law of Ukraine «On Stimulating the Development of Regions», the Law of Ukraine «On the Development and State Support of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ukraine», the Law of Ukraine «On Providing Assistance to the In-

sured persons for the period of implementation of restrictive anti-epidemic measures introduced to prevent the spread of the acute respiratory disease COVID-19 caused by the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus, the Law of Ukraine «On the permit system in the sphere of economic activity», the Law of Ukraine «On stimulating the development of the digital economy in Ukraine» and other legal acts.

In the Ivano-Frankivsk region, the «Regional target program for the development of small and medium-sized enterprises in the Ivano-Frankivsk region for 2022–2023» was approved (Decision of the regional council dated November 12, 2021, No. 280-10/2021). The main priority tasks of the Program should be considered: financial support of business entities; development of entrepreneurial culture and improvement of the level of professional training of entrepreneurs; promoting the development of elements of infrastructure supporting entrepreneurship at the regional level; promoting the development and activation of dialogue between business, government, and society; involving business entities to participate in international programs and projects.

Also, an important niche in the development of the region is occupied by the «Program of socio-economic and cultural development of the Ivano-Frankivsk region for 2023» (Decree of the Ivano-Frankivsk Regional Military Administration dated January 12, 2023, No. 10). In modern conditions, regional industrial policy is aimed at preserving and effectively realizing the production potential of regional enterprises, reorienting the structure of production in accordance with the requirements of wartime, carrying out effective measures to ensure the restoration of the activities of relocated business entities, expanding the network of industrial parks as the main sites for attracting investment resources and creation of new jobs.

Currently, there are registered industrial parks in Ivano-Frankivsk region, including:

- Industrial Park «Dolyna» was included in the Register of Industrial Parks on February 3, 2014. The initiator of its creation was the Dolyna City Council.

The industrial park was created for 30 years. The area of the land plot is 27.14 hectares.

The managing company is the «Dolyna-Invest» utility company of the Dolyna City Council. The purpose of creating an industrial (industrial) park is the formation of mechanisms to effectively meet the demand of

investors for sites prepared for the placement of industrial facilities, logistics and related services.

Light, food, woodworking and automobile industries are considered priority areas of activity for determining the functional purpose of the industrial park.

– The industrial park «Kalush Industrial HUB» was included in the Register of Industrial Parks on August 30, 2021. The initiator of the creation of the industrial park is LLC «Ch.A.S.».

The term for which the industrial park is being created is 30 years. The total area is 18.7306 hectares (privately owned land).

The purpose of creation: ensuring the economic development of the city of Kalush, the Ivano–Frankivsk region and Ukraine as a whole, as well as the activation of investment and economic activity, increasing the level of employment of the population, the development of modern production and logistics infrastructure.

Functional purpose: mechanical engineering; production of machines and devices of the electro-technical industry; woodworking and furniture production; metalworking industry; production of finishing materials; production of construction and thermal insulation materials; processing of polymers, production of plastic products; other purpose (depending on the urgency of placing a specific production on the territory of the community).

Unregistered industrial parks also operate on the territory of Ivano–Frankivsk region. For example, in October 2014, the Burshtyn city council approved the concept and created the Burshtyn industrial park. The total area is 37 hectares. The project of the land management of the site has been prepared. 243.2 thousand hryvnias were used from the city budget for the arrangement of the park.

In the city of Ivano–Frankivsk, since 2019, the private industrial park «Arkan» has been operating with an area of 19.3 hectares.

The industrial park is located on the territory of PJSC «Ivano–Frankivsk Armature Plant», which is connected to all necessary communications (electrical substation, own water sources, sewage main, gas distribution station).

The industrial park is focused on the development of machine tool construction, robotics, instrument construction, electrical engineering industry, household machines and appliances, etc.

Therefore, the «Program of socio–economic and cultural development of Ivano–Frankivsk region for 2023» defines the development of engineering and

transport infrastructure and the introduction of financial and investment incentives in the territories of industrial parks, which are registered, in particular, «Kalush Industrial HUB», industrial park «Dolyna», industrial park «Burshtyn», industrial park «Arkan», industrial park «Bodnariv», industrial park «Rozhnyativ», preparation of project documentation. Also, considerable attention is paid to the development of the innovation ecosystem of Ivano–Frankivsk by launching its components on the basis of the center «Promprylad. Renovation», namely the organization of the open workshop of the largest innovation center of Western Ukraine «Promprylad. Renovation», implementation of the project «New economy of Ivano–Frankivsk – support of new clusters of innovative economic activity in Ivano–Frankivsk»; organization of the work of the Business Support Center and co–working in the modern innovation center «Promprylad. Renovation»; the development of new investment projects that will be able to participate in the competition of regional development projects to receive sectoral budget support from the EU, the implementation of the UNDP project «Strengthening the resilience of communities in the regions of Ukraine»; implementation of mechanisms for the implementation of innovative sectoral and cross–sectoral priorities, including through the promotion system, in particular, on the 3S platform, and the creation of appropriate incentives, etc.

On the initiative of the President of Ukraine, the State Program «Affordable Loans 5–7–9%» was introduced in 2020, the purpose of which is to simplify the access of micro and small businesses to bank lending. Credit agreements were signed by business representatives of the Ivano–Frankivsk region as part of the implementation of the State program «Affordable loans 5–7–9%».

The «Development Strategy of the Ivano–Frankivsk Region for 2021–2027» defines a list of sectoral priorities for smart specialization, among which it is worth noting:

- production of basic chemical products, fertilizers and nitrogen compounds, plastics and synthetic rubber in primary forms;
- production of rubber tires, tires and inner tubes;
- retreading of rubber tires and tires;
- production of cement, lime and gypsum mixtures;
- production of abrasive products and non–metallic mineral products;
- production of other primary steel processing products;

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- production of electric motors, generators, transformers, electrical distribution and control equipment;
- production of machines and general purpose equipment;
- production of games and toys;
- intake, purification and supply of water. These types of activities are characterized by significant dynamics in terms of the share of employed people and can stimulate the growth of production volumes in related types of economic activity by creating clusters.

Therefore, the key issue of the «Development Strategy of the Ivano–Frankivsk Region for 2021–2027» (Decision of the Regional Council of February 21, 2020, No. 1381–34/2020) is economic development as a process of strategic partnership, which helps to accelerate the growth of productivity of the local economy stimulating investments in new and existing enterprises with high potential for growth, creating conditions for this development for a long period. The possibilities of such development should also include the creation of industrial, technological, innovation parks, etc. (according to the Development Strategy of the Ivano–Frankivsk Region for 2021–2027, operational goal 1.1. stimulation of the development of innovative types of economic activity, investment attraction involves task 1.1.2. «Preparation and support of investment projects (creation of industrial and technological parks): concept and technical and economic rationale for the placement of industrial parks; development of engineering infrastructure for industrial parks).

The main tasks of cluster initiatives in the Ivano–Frankivsk region and in Ukraine in the war and post–war periods include:

- ensuring the development of an appropriate legislative framework for the formation of favorable conditions for the development of entrepreneurship in Ukraine with a special emphasis on the support of network structures – clusters (the development of a legal framework for the creation and functioning of clusters, in particular, it is necessary to define at the legislative level the concepts of «cluster», «cluster policy», «clusterization»; development and implementation of the state program to promote the development of clusters; creation of the Register of Clusters in Ukraine);
- development and formation of types of industrial activity with higher added value (identification of priority sectors of industry at the level of regions,

creation of cluster associations and other forms of organization of innovative activity; preparation and submission of proposals for the introduction of a preferential tax regime for enterprises producing high–tech and innovative products at the expense of own investment resources);

- increasing the influence and responsibility of local authorities in conditions of decentralization in relation to ensuring the development of clusters;

- implementation of an effective cluster policy, which is possible in the context of a set of measures to significantly improve the investment climate of the region;

- development of models for using the public–private partnership mechanism in order to attract non–state investment resources for the development of clusters, first of all, providing the territory with the necessary infrastructure;

- carrying out an assessment of the consequences of military actions for the development of clusters in the regions of Ukraine;

- development of a step–by–step action plan for the restoration of the functioning of industrial enterprises on an innovative basis for the short– and medium–term post–war period;

- providing state and donor financial support for the development of clusters, updating the material and technical base, in particular: funds that will be allocated within the framework of the European plan for Ukraine (The «Marshall Plan»); aid, investments, soft loans (USA); bilateral assistance at the country level in the form of grants, credit guarantees, loans, etc. for the reconstruction of certain infrastructure facilities; assistance from international institutions (the World Bank and the EBRD, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) (Danylyshyn, 2022); special sources of financing (the Solidarity Trust Fund of Ukraine, the Ukrainian Fund for the Restoration of Property and Destroyed Infrastructure); private investments, investments of domestic and international businesses;

- legislative definition of the mechanism for creating cross–border clusters, which can become an effective mechanism for accelerating European integration processes. In particular, the conclusion of bilateral agreements on the creation of cross–border clusters at the level of governments of participating countries, coordination of strategies and plans for the development of national parts of cross–border clusters. The experience of the operation of such

structures in certain border regions of the EU shows their positive impact on the socio-economic development and international cooperation of the participating countries, the stimulation of business activity, the inflow of investments and the solution of employment problems in the border territories.

The adoption of appropriate measures for the development of clusters in the Ivano-Frankivsk region in the post-war period will contribute to: increasing the level of innovative culture in the region; activation of innovative activities in the region due to the accumulation of knowledge of a commercial and industrial nature, internal competition between manufacturers, cooperation between manufacturers and suppliers, etc.; development of production of competitive products with high added value; the growth of tax revenues to budgets as a result of attracting investments, including foreign ones; increasing the level of scientific and industrial cooperation and integration between representatives of science and the real sector of the economy; growth of the share of export of finished products; creation of unique opportunities for the training of highly qualified specialists outside the boundaries of industry training.

Conclusions

The theoretical foundations of the creation and development of the national innovation system in the period of globalization are substantiated. In addition, among the priority issues that were considered in the research process, it is necessary to note such as the patterns of development of the national innovation system. In particular, the openness of the national innovation system, the determination of the role of the state in innovation development, the technological levels of innovation development, the identification of the role of the region in the development of innovation, the role of innovation in the process of globalization.

Considering the above, the creation of a national innovation system in the conditions of globalization is the main direction of ensuring competitiveness. Therefore, special attention was paid to the issue of regulatory and legal support for the development of elements of the national innovation system on the example of the Ivano-Frankivsk region. This is a promising direction for the region of Ukraine in the war and post-war period. Therefore, for this purpose, proposals were developed for the creation and development of clusters in the Ivano-Frankivsk re-

gion, as one of the western regions of Ukraine. In particular, the development of a legislative framework for the formation of a network of clusters in Ukraine; development and formation of types of industrial activity with high added value; implementation of an effective cluster policy; provision of state and donor financial support for the development of clusters, etc.

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